

Power Law and Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

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In (1), a generalized n -dimensional vector probability is computed and shown to lead to a power law distribution in the argument $(1 - p^2/RR)$ where $E = 1/2m RR$ and $E = eave n$ (n =number of particles) with power $(n-3)/2$ which in turn leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in the high n limit. In (2), it is argued that a gas of particles moving in one-dimension also leads to a power law distribution in $(E - e_i)$ (where $e_i = p^2/2m$ for the i th particle), but with a different power from the vector solution. This result also leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in the large n limit. Both of these approaches are in keeping with the microcanonical prescription, i.e. a fixed total energy $E = eave n$.

In this note, we try to relate $P(e_1)P(e_2)$ to $P(e_1+e_2)$, within the microcanonical approaches mentioned above in order to examine the relationship between the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and a power law one. We also argue that a consideration of the argument $F(E - e) = F(E \exp(-e/E))$ for $e \ll E$ with $E = eave n$ suggests a power law in the high n limit if one is to have a probability independent of n .

Microcanonical Distribution for a Vector and One-Dimensional Gas

(1) and (2) deal with finding a single particle distribution, subject to the microcanonical constraint of a fixed energy. (1) deals with a n -dimensional vector and (2) with n one-dimensional particles. Both approaches, then consider the large n limit of the distribution and show that it leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

Here, instead we consider the relationship of $P(e_1)P(e_2)$ and $P(e_1+e_2)$ in the high n limit to see how this may lead to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and at the same time point to a power law distribution, at least for high n . This approach may help to explain why two different probability distributions, namely one for an n -dimensional vector and the other for n 1-dimensional particles, both lead to the same Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

Before doing this, we briefly consider both approaches. The first approach, the vector one, relies on the relationship:

$$\sum_i p(i)^2/2m = RR \quad ((1))$$

Here $p(i)$ represents the momentum for the n th component of the vector. We note that a vector is defined in terms of physical rotations, usually in space for the 3-dimensional case. We argue that even for a n -dimensional vector, the notion of rotation must be present. It is this sense of rotation which defines the probability distribution. For example, in (3), the probability distribution associated with a 2-dimensional vector is present. The key idea seems to be to focus on $d\theta$ i.e.

$$P(\theta) d\theta = C_1 d\theta \quad \text{where } C_1 \text{ is a constant} \quad ((2))$$

If one were not dealing with a vector, one would not introduce an angle θ a priori and state that probability is constant for θ . Given a vector (B_x, B_y) :

$$B_x = B \cos(\theta) \text{ so } dB_x = -B \sin(\theta) d\theta \text{ or } C_1 d\theta = C_1 dB_x / \{B \sin(\theta)\} \quad ((3))$$

In other words, one cannot uniformly pick a value B_x in its interval because the constant probability is associated with θ . ((3)) is simply a rewrite of ((2)) in terms of different variables.

In (1), this same approach is used, but applied to a n -dimensional vector. The basic idea is to assign a value p_p to the n th component so that $RR - p_p$ is the variable proportional to the energy left for the remaining $n-1$ components. These satisfy:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} p_p(i) = RR - p_p \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is the equation of an $n-1$ dimensional sphere and points may be equally distributed over its surface. Thus, the probability $P(p_p)$ is proportional to the area of the $n-1$ sphere. Given that one has an n -dimensional vector, use is again made of the angle θ , namely:

$$R \cos(\theta) = p_n \text{ where } p_n \text{ is the value of the } n\text{th component of the } n\text{-vector.}$$

Now probability is given by the area of the $n-1$ dimensional sphere multiplied by $R d\theta$ where R is a constant (i.e. $E_{\text{total}} = 1/2m RR$) i.e.

Area $(n-1) * R d\theta$ ((5)) which is shown in (1) to be proportional to:

$$\sqrt{1 - p_p/RR}^{\text{power}(n-3)} \quad ((5))$$

The sqrt follows from the surface area of an $n-1$ sphere. The $R d\theta$ piece does not contribute in the high n limit.

In (2), a vector was not considered, but rather it was assumed that for two particles (1-dimensional motion), one could take any energy value between 0 and E with uniform probability. For $n=3$ particles, the first particle has energy e , the second e_2 may have any value from 0 to $E-e$ with uniform probability, the third any value from 0 to $E-e-e_2$ and the last receives the remaining energy. In (2) it was shown that in general one has a probability:

$$P(e)de = C (E-e)^{\text{power}(n-2)} \quad ((6))$$

((5)) and ((6)) differ even given that one is a function of p and the other of $e=p/2m$. Both expressions, however, in the high n limit become: $\exp(-p/2mT)$ where T is a parameter. We ask: Is it possible to anticipate this result without using explicit models like the n -vector approach or uniform probabilities?

High n (number of particles) Functions

We note that in calculating the probability $P(e)$, i.e the probability for one particle to have energy e with the rest having $E-e$, one considers the number of ways of distributing $E-e$ energy to the $n-1$ particles without any bias. Now:

$$E = e(\text{ave}) n \quad ((7))$$

If n is large due to the physical situation, such as a gas:

$$E - e = E(1 - e/n) \text{ approx} = E \{ \exp(-e/(e(\text{ave}) n)) \} \quad ((8))$$

Assume that one does not know the probability function. Then:

$$P(e) = F \{ \exp(-e/(e(\text{ave}) n)) \} \quad ((9))$$

Let e be a small value compared with E . Then:

$$P(e) = F(E) + e \frac{dF}{de} (\text{at } E) \quad ((10))$$

For $e_1, e_2 \ll E$

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) \text{ approx} = F(E)F(E) + F(E) \frac{dF}{de} (e_1 + e_2) \quad (\text{with } dF/de \text{ evaluated at } E) \quad ((11))$$

((11)), however, is equivalent to: $P(e_1 + e_2)$ to first order ((12)) so:

$$P(e_1 + e_2) = P(e_1)P(e_2) \quad ((13))$$

Here in ((13)) no use of any explicit model has been made and no assumption of a power law occurs. A solution of ((13)) is $\exp(-e/T)$ which, however, is the high n limit of the two different power law results from (1) and (2). At first, it seems that ((13)) is not linked to a power law at all, but if one considers ((9)), and imagines two cases, one with n particles (n being a very large number) and one with $2n$ particles, one might expect $P(e)$ to be the same in both cases. This holds for $3n, 4n$ etc. Thus, one would expect ((9)) to be independent of n for large n . This immediately suggests a power law at high n , namely:

$$\exp(-e/E) \text{ power}(an) = \exp(-e/T) \quad ((14))$$

where T is a parameter which may be associated with the average energy per particle and normalization.

In the n -vector approach, $a = .5$ so $E = e(\text{ave}) n$ or $2 e(\text{ave}) = T$ for a 1-dimensional problem. This matches the Maxwell-Boltzmann results.

The uniform probability (non-vector) approach leads to $P(e)$ proportional to $(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$. In such a case, $P(e)$ is proportional to $\exp(-e/e(\text{ave}))$, but $e(\text{ave})$ should be replaced with T and the following conditions imposed:

$$\int dp \exp(-pp/2mT) C = 1 \quad ((15a)) \text{ and } \int C dp pp/2m \exp(-pp/2mT) = e(\text{ave}). \quad ((15b))$$

The result of ((15b)) depends on the form $e=pp/2m$ because one has a gamma function result which together with $C=\sqrt{3.14*2mT}$ dictates the relationship between $e(\text{ave})$ and T .

We note that the difference in the approaches of (1) and (2) is not linked with $d\theta$, but rather with the number of states arranged over an $n-1$ sphere with area proportional to $\sqrt{RR-pp}$ where $E=RR/2m$ versus $(E-e)$ being used in the uniform probability scenario. This is what gives rise to $n/2$ versus n as the power of $(1-e/E)$ in the high n limit.

We argue, however, in this section that the requirement that ((9)) be independent of n and the fact that $e \ll E$ so $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_1+e_2)$ seem to lead, first to a power law (in the high n case) which becomes the Maxwell-Boltzmann condition, and simply the Maxwell-Boltzmann condition in the second case. One may note that the power law condition appears when one considers e relative to $E_{\text{total}} = e(\text{ave}) n$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that although there exist specific models based on a constrained total energy E (e.g. (1),(2)), in the high n limit, one may use the ideas of the constrained total energy (i.e. microcanonical distribution) leading to a function in $F(E-e) = F(E(1-e/E)) = F(E \exp(-e/(e(\text{ave}) n)))$. If one wishes the “ n ” to disappear, then in the high n case, one would expect a power law $F(E \exp(-e/(e(\text{ave}) n)))$ proportional to $\exp(-e/(e(\text{ave}) n))$ power (an) where a is some number. This leads to a distribution of $\exp(-e/T_1)$ which may be used to fix T_1 using normalization and an average energy expression. As a result, one may predict a power law distribution which yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann result. In this case, $e(\text{ave}) = .5T$ which is in keeping with an n -vector result for high n . A uniform probability approach (2) leads to a power law $(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$ which leads to $\exp(-e/e(\text{ave}))$.

An alternative approach using $F(E-e) = F(E) + e dF/de$ (at E) leads to $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2)$ which bypasses the power law form and immediately leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

References

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